

EMERGING ANTIFUNGAL RESISTANCE IN BIOFILM-FORMING *CANDIDA* SPECIES ISOLATED FROM MEDICAL DEVICES: A MOLECULAR CHARACTERIZATION STUDY

Muhammad Abdullah¹, Muhammad Saqib Khalil², Naila Gulfam³

^{1,2}Srhad Institute of Allied Health Sciences, Sarhad University of Science and Information Technology

³Jinnah College For women, University of Peshawar

*saqib.siahs@suit.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *

Muhammad Saqib Khalil

Abstract

Biofilm formation by *Candida* species is a significant factor contributing antifungal resistance, leading to persistent infections and increased healthcare burden. Biofilms enhance the survival of *Candida* species on medical devices complicating treatment and increasing the risk of systemic infections. This study aimed to isolate and molecularly characterize antifungal resistance profiling biofilm-forming *Candida* species from medical devices used in tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar, Pakistan. Samples of 400 medical devices were collected from various sections of Lady Reading Hospital (LRH), Hayatabad Medical complex (HMC) and Khyber Teaching Hospital (KTH). The devices included urine catheters (19.5%), central venous catheters (8.75%), endotracheal tubes (11.75%), ventilator masks (13.75%), intrauterine devices (18%), dental implants (7%), and syringes/ cannulas (6.5%). Identification of *Candida* species was based on differential growth on chromogenic agar, which allowed for differentiation based on colony pigmentation. Congo red agar assay was performed to assess biofilm formation. Molecular characterization by 18S rRNA analysis and phylogenetic trees were constructed. The most prevalent of the 16 isolated *Candida* species was *Candida albicans* (43.75%), followed by *Candida glabrata* (25%), *Candida tropicalis* (18.75%) and *Candida krusei* (12.5%); all the isolated strains were biofilm producers. Congo red agar assay confirmed the biofilm-forming potential of these isolates. FTIR spectroscopy revealed the presence of important groups in the biofilm matrix, including protein polysaccharides, lipids, and hydroxyl-containing compounds that are essential for biofilm stability. This study demonstrates the cellular and chemical challenges of biofilm formation in *Candida* species isolated from medical devices. The chromogenic agar assay was shown to be useful for organism identification, while the Congo red assay confirmed the potential for biofilm formation. These findings highlight the urgent need for antifungal strategies to combat biofilm-associated infections in clinical settings.

INTRODUCTION

The fungal kingdom is incredibly diverse, and its members can inhabit an extraordinarily wide range of niches. Surprisingly, despite this

remarkable versatility, relatively few species are regularly encountered as pathogens of humans. Although some of these fungi are primary pathogens, which cause human disease in the

absence of any known defect in infected individuals, there is a second group of fungi that are opportunistic pathogens like *Candida* species (Staniszewska *et al.*, 2020).

The genus *Candida* belongs to the Fungi kingdom, class of *Deuteromycetes*, and includes between 150 and 200 species, such as yeasts with *ascomycetous* and *basidiomycetous* affinities. *Candida* spp. are the leading cause of invasive fungal infection in the clinical setting (Nett *et al.*, 2020). Currently just over 40 of more than 200 known *Candida* species have been implicated in human infection, although for many years it has been recognized that only a few cause invasive infection on a regular basis (Mishra *et al.*, 2021). Despite the predominance of *Candida albicans*, non-*albicans* *Candida* species such as *Candida glabrata*, *Candida tropicalis*, *Candida guilliermondii*, *Candida dubliniensis*, *Candida parapsilosis*, and *Candida krusei* are emerging as both colonizers and pathogens that can cause superficial and systemic infections (Anh *et al.*, 2021).

This infection occurs more frequently in pregnant women compared to non-pregnant women a consequence of the high circulating estrogen in pregnancy which facilitates the adherence of *Candida* to the vagina mucosa. This is responsible for the more severe symptoms and persistent infections that are typical of vaginal candidiasis in pregnancy. *Candida albicans* is the most common specie of *Candida* associated with vaginal candidiasis in pregnancy, however, other species such as *Candida glabrata*, *Candida tropicalis*, *Candida krusei*, *Candida parapsilosis*, *Candida pseudotropicalis* and *Candida stellatoidea* are increasingly becoming important (Sule-Odu *et al.*, 2020). Vaginal discharge syndrome (VDS) is the most common gynaecological condition among women of reproductive age. Vulvovaginal candidiasis (VVC) is the most common aetiology of VDS, accounting for about 90% of symptomatic vaginal infections. Up to 75% of healthy women face symptomatic VVC at least once in their childbearing years, with some experiencing intermittent and often obdurate forms of the disease (Dunaiski *et al.*, 2022).

Candida colonisation of the oral cavity increases

in immunocompromised individuals which leads to the development of oral candidiasis. In addition, host factors such as xerostomia, smoking, oral prostheses, dental caries, diabetes and cancer treatment accelerate the disease process. *Candida albicans* is the primary causative agent of this infection, owing to its ability to form biofilm and hyphae and to produce hydrolytic enzymes and candidalysin (Patel *et al.*, 2021).

Esophageal candidiasis (EC) is the most common esophageal infection. *Candida albicans* *C. albicans*, the most important fungal pathogen in humans, is a gastrointestinal commensal that forms colonies on the esophagus in up to 20% of people. The incidence of EC is 0.3–5.2% in the general population, but is much higher in patients with severe immunodeficiency, such as human immunodeficiency virus (HIV)-infected patient (Ogiso *et al.*, 2021).

Candida spp. cause infections that range from non-life-threatening mucosal illnesses to invasive fatal infections, such as bloodstream infections. Nosocomial infection by *Candida* is a problematic issue outbreaks worldwide. *Candida* spp. are currently ranked fourth and sixth among the causative agents of nosocomial bloodstream infections (BSI) in the USA and Europe, respectively. Egypt showed the highest *Candida* BSI burden, compared to the other Middle East neighboring countries (El-Ganiny *et al.*, 2021).

. In the hospitals, have been reported due to sub-optimal hospital care practices and contaminated environment, whereas outbreaks in the community is related to spurious practices by untrained healthcare providers. According to (Chakrabarti *et al.*, 2020) table 1.1 show the percentage of candidiasis among risk groups in hospitals in the region of asia. In Pakistan, *C. tropicalis* has been reported as the most common species in adults with invasive candidiasis accounting for about 38% of cases followed by *C. parapsilosis* (17.8%), *C. glabrata* (15.9%), and *C. albicans* (12.3%) (Sayeed *et al.*, 2020). As Pakistan is included in stone belt region with high rates of nephrolithiatic patients, local population is at high risk for complicated urinary tract infection with stone disease especially catheterized patients.

There is no data on prevalence of *Candida* infection among local patient to identify their possible role as causative agent of recurrent and

UTI in nephrolithiatic patients (Zafar *et al.*, 2020).

Table No: 1 shows the percentage of candida infection according to (Chakrabarti *et al.*, 2020).

Risk groups in Hospitals	Infection
Heart (5-20%)	Candidiasis (50-60%)
Small bowel	Candidiasis (80%)
Pancreas	Candidiasis (75%)
Hematological malignancy undergoing chemotherapy (5-30%)	Candidiasis (25-50%)
Chronic granulomatous disease (20-40%)	Candidiasis (10-15%)
Exogenous steroid therapy	Candidiasis (40%)
Diabetes	Candidiasis (most common)
Anti-TNF therapy	Candidiasis (23%)
HIV infected patients	Oropharyngeal candidiasis (Up to 75%)
Transplant patients (3-20%)	Invasive candidiasis (30-70%)
Kidney (0-20%)	Invasive candidiasis (50%)
Liver (5-40%)	Candidiasis (20-25%)

Hospital acquired infections (HAI) are considered a public health problem, by increasing mortality and morbidity, increasing the length of hospitalization and very high costs for healthcare (Voidazan *et al.*, 2020). The use of implanted medical devices such as prosthetic joints, catheters, and breast implants continues to expand. These devices are associated with a small but clinically important risk of foreign body infection (Stewart *et al.*, 2020). Patients in intensive care units (ICUs) are at high risk for healthcare-acquired infections (HAI) due to the high prevalence of invasive procedures and devices, induced immunosuppression, comorbidity, frailty and increased age (Blot *et al.*, 2022). Because of the intrinsic properties of metal materials such as high strength, mechanical reliability, elasticity, good corrosion resistance, wear resistance and fatigue, toughness, and thermal and electrical conductivity make medical metal devices predominate over other materials, it is estimated that between 70% and 80% of implants world level are metallic (Festas *et al.*, 2020). Surface adhesion is a critical first step for biofilm formation and skin colonization. For *C. albicans* and other *Candida* spp. Initially,

microbial (fungal) cells arrive at the device surface and attach, driven by their propensity to settle onto a solid substrate rather than remaining in the planktonic state. Once a sufficient number of cells is attached, intercellular communication causes a switch in phenotype resulting in the production of extracellular matrix and biofilm formation (Garvey *et al.*, 2023). Members of the agglutin-like sequence (ALS) family of adhesins function in adherence and as virulence factors in *Candida* species and homologs to ALS family proteins have been identified in *C. auris* (Horton *et al.*, 2023).

The property of microorganisms to adhere to different surfaces facilitates the formation of biofilm in clinical settings such as catheters, prosthetic heart valves, joints, and various tissues in the host leading to effective colonization and this results in persistent drug-resistant (Atriwal *et al.*, 2021). Biofilm formation in fungi is a well-organized process that progresses through coordinated early, intermediate, and maturation stages. It begins with attachment of a microorganism to a surface, followed by a cascade of differential gene expression resulting in biofilm formation. Adhesion of fungi to a surface can also

be facilitated by formation of an organic conditioning layer, which may include compounds released by the host inflammatory response, in serum, saliva, or vaginal excretions (Li *et al.*, 2021).

Directly or indirectly, biofilms are responsible for over 80% of all microbial infections. Which can vary from superficial to more serious and deep infections, with high mortality rates associated. *Candida* species biofilms are among the most common microorganisms in clinical settings, being commonly found in patients' skin or on the hands of nursing staff adhered to biomedical devices, growing as biofilms, capable of withstanding extraordinarily high antifungal concentrations. The first description of a *Candida albicans* biofilms from oral and urinary sources was made in 1981, and since then our overall appreciation and under testing of them has improved (Ramage *et al.*, 2023).

Medical device-associated infections (MDAI) comprise 50–70% of all. MDAI are mostly originated from the formation of pathogenic biofilms on the device surface (Carvalho *et al.* 2020). According to data from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), of nearly 2 million nosocomial infections, 50–70% were related to MD. Mortality attributed to DRIs is strongly associated with the type of device, ranging from <5% for devices such as Foley catheters to >25% for central venous catheters (CVCs). The three most common DRIs are centerline-associated bloodstream infection (CRBSIs), ventilator-associated pneumonia, and Foley catheter-associated urinary tract infection (Folliero *et al.*, 2021).

As for all medical devices, however, the function and safety of these devices may be jeopardized by microbial biofilm. The biofilm may negatively impact the function of the device, with consequences for the patient. Most bacteria and *candida* can form biofilm, an assemblage of microorganisms irreversibly attached to a surface, limiting their removal. Biofilm can be formed on both cells and abiotic surfaces, e.g., medical devices and urinary catheters. The expression of biofilm is promoted by different virulence factors

(Slettengren *et al.*, 2020). It is estimated that out of all hospital infections, 65% are caused due to biofilms (Ali *et al.*, 2021).

Candida spp produces highly structured biofilms composed of multiple cell types (i.e., round, budding yeast-form cells; oval pseudohyphal cells; and elongated, cylindrical hyphal cells) encased in an extracellular matrix. Accounting for 15% of all hospital-acquired sepsis cases, species within the CTG (Cytosine Thymine Guanine) clade (predominantly *C. albicans*, but including several closely related species as well) are the fourth most frequent cause of bloodstream infections in clinical settings and are the predominant fungal species isolated from medical device infections. Urinary and central venous catheters, pacemakers, mechanical heart valves, joint prostheses, contact lenses, and dentures are all susceptible to *C. albicans* biofilms (Mottley *et al.*, 2021).

Biofilms are multicellular structures adhered to solid surfaces using self-produced cellular proteins and a highly hydrated extracellular polymeric matrix. Pathogenic biofilms on implanted devices such as catheters and cardiovascular devices are of significant concern in medical device-associated infection, causing serious threats to patient health and impairment of device function, ultimately leading to treatment failures. The formation of biofilm in medical devices constitutes a series of complex mechanisms. Due to their high tolerance to antimicrobial drugs and host defense mechanisms (Ajetunmobi *et al.*, 2023).

A number of resistance mechanisms, including overexpression of membrane-localized drug efflux pumps, alteration in drug targets, metabolic salvage pathways, and Changes in membrane sterol composition have been proposed to account for the antifungal resistance of planktonic *C. albicans*. Recent studies have suggested that *C. albicans* can also exhibit resistance against CAS, mediated by mutation of genes encoding 1,3- β -glucan synthase enzyme overexpression of Sbe2p, a Golgi protein involved in transport of cell wall components, or drug efflux mediated by Cdr2p, a membrane-localized

ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporter (Deng *et al.*, 2021).

For many *Candida* species, formation of a biofilm allows the cells to tolerate antifungals at concentrations many fold greater than those needed to kill their planktonic counterparts. The degree of this biofilm associated drug resistance varies by species and antifungal, with biofilms withstanding up to 1000×-fold higher concentrations of antifungals compared to planktonic cells (Horton *et al.*, 2020). Another major contributing element toward resistance is persister cells, which are the inconsequential subset of yeast cells with minimum metabolic activity assumed to be raised as a phenotypic variant but not a mutant type. They are highly resistant cells within biofilms. Amphotericin B treatment upon *Candida* species led to the discovery of persister cells. These cells are acknowledged to be persister as they maintain themselves in a dormant stage. Still, in a stressful situation, they reactivate themselves to a state of active metabolism and reinstate as biofilms. Subsequently, drug sequestration by persister cells occurs due to some virulent traits like hyphal growth rather than an expression of efflux pumps and cell membrane structure (Raheem *et al.*, 2019).

There are several approaches to develop new antibiofilm treatments, ranging from the development of new chemical entities that act on novel selective biofilm targets, to modifying existing antifungal drugs or repurposing existing drugs, primarily used to treat conditions other than fungal infections. A chemical modification on the echinocandin backbone for example resulted in an increased stability of echinocandin CD101, allowing the use of this antibiofilm drug as a topical agent for skin and vaginal infections (Tits *et al.*, 2020).

To prevent *Candida* biofilms, non-clinically used small molecules and peptides with inherent antifungal and antibiofilm properties can be highly effective. Filastatin, a potent small molecule inhibitor of *Candida* attachment and filamentation (Filamentation is a critical step in the formation of biofilms, which are structured

communities of fungal cells that are highly resistant to antifungal treatments), was recently identified in a screen of 30,000 compounds. It has been found that incubating *Candida albicans* with various biomaterials in the presence of filastatin can inhibit *Candida* attachment to these materials (Vera-González *et al.*, 2020). Antimicrobial lock therapy (ALT) generally involves instilling a solution into the lumen of a central venous catheter (CVC) that combines an antimicrobial agent, at concentrations 100-1000 times higher than the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for planktonic cells, with an anticoagulant. This solution is allowed to dwell, or "lock," in the catheter when it is not in use, to prevent colonization or sterilize an existing infection (Kovács *et al.*, 2022).

Fatty acids are essential to the functioning of every known form of life. Fatty acids have anti-hyphal and antibiofilm effects when used at quantities below their MICs. The biofilm formation of many pathogenic microorganisms, including *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Candida albicans*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and others, is inhibited or slowed by adding certain fatty acids. Oleic acid and linoleic acid inhibit *Candida* biofilm and filament formation without impacting planktonic cell proliferation (Alem *et al.*, 2022).

METHODOLOGY

Research Center

The research was conducted in the laboratory of Microbiology, Sarhad Institute of Allied Health Sciences, SUIT, Peshawar.

Study Design

The research study was employed a descriptive / observational study design. This research design was aimed to gather samples at a specific moment to evaluate the prevalence and resistance characteristics of *Candida* species that formed biofilms on medical devices. Additionally, the study sought to identify and characterize these biofilms.

Study period

The research work was completed in total 12

months (from June 2023 to June 2024).

Inclusion

- Medical devices used in tertiary care hospitals, such as urinary catheters, central venous catheters, prosthetic devices, endotracheal tubes, or other devices capable of producing biofilm were included.
- Isolates were collected within a specified time frame to capture current resistance profiles.

Exclusion

- *Candida* isolates that were not associated with biofilm formation on medical devices were excluded.
- *Candida* isolates obtained from environmental sources rather than from biofilms on medical devices were also excluded.
- Only *Candida* samples were included, while other fungal isolates, bacterial isolates, and duplicate isolates obtained from the same medical devices were eliminated.

Sample Size

A total of 400 samples were taken. The sample size was determined using Yamane's formula:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \times p \times (1-p)}{E^2}$$

n = Sample size.

P = standard deviation 0.5 (safe choice).

Z = Z-score corresponding to the chosen confidence level.

E = Desired margin of error (5% which will be 0.05 in decimal).

Sample Collection and Preliminary Identification

The collected samples in a sterile gel tube were transported to the laboratory for identification and processing.

Primary Isolation of *Candida spp*

The most frequently used primary isolation medium for *Candida* species is Sabouraud Dextrose agar (SDA) and Blood agar. After sample collection the swab stick was streak on SDA and Blood agar plates. All samples were cultured through streaking on SDA and Blood

agar, then was incubated aerobically at 37°C for 24-48 hours. After incubation, if mixed growth was observed on the agar, it was then sub cultured and purify the growth of *candida spp* (Kim *et al.*, 2016).

Microscopic Identification

Direct microscopic features were observed using gram stain. A small sample of a *Candida* colony was transferred to create a thin smear. The smear was air-dried and then heat-fixed to ensure that the cells adhered to the slide. The slide was first stained with crystal violet, which stained all cells purple. After rinsing, iodine solution was applied, acting as a mordant to fix the crystal violet inside the cells. The slide was then decolorized with ethanol or acetone. A counterstaining step followed, where safranin was applied, turning the cells into dark purple. Finally, the slide was rinsed and dried, ready for microscopic examination. Under the microscope, *Candida* cells appeared as purple, oval or round cells, often exhibiting budding, characteristic of their morphology (Kim *et al.*, 2016).

Chromogenic Assay

All the pure culture of *candida* species were streaked on chrome agar (Vignesh Kanna *et al.*, 2017), it is differential media for all types of *candida* isolates. They were kept for about 24 hours in the incubator at 37c for a proper growth. After 24 to 48 hours colony morphology and colour of the colony was interpreted as per manufacturer's specifications. It showed growth of different *Candida* species produce colonies of various colors on CHROMagar.

Determination of Biofilm Formation

Congo Red Agar

The CRA (Congo red agar) method was done according to the protocol of (Kıvanç *et al.*, 2020). The constituents of media were, brain heart infusion broth 37 g/l, sucrose 0.8 g/l, agar-agar 10 g/l and Congo red stain 0.8 g/l. All the chemicals were supplied from Himedia. Congo red stain was prepared as a concentrated aqueous solution, autoclaved separately and added to the

media when the agar had cooled to 55 °C. Plates of the medium were inoculated and incubated aerobically for 24 h at 37 °C. After incubation biofilm formation shows blackish color on colony surface.

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy

To analyze *Candida* biofilms using Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, biofilms are first grown on suitable substrates and then carefully removed, rinsed, and dried completely. The dried biofilm is ground into a fine powder and mixed with potassium bromide (KBr) powder, which is then pressed into transparent discs. These KBr discs containing the biofilm are placed in an FTIR spectrometer, and spectra are acquired in the range of 400 to 4,000 cm⁻¹. The spectra are analyzed to identify characteristic peaks corresponding to various functional groups like proteins, polysaccharides, lipids, and nucleic acids, thus providing detailed insights into the chemical composition and structure of the biofilm (Singhalage *et al.*, 2018).

Antifungal Susceptibility Testing (AFT)

Antifungal susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method. The procedure involved preparing a homogenous suspension of the fungal isolate in sterile saline, adjusting its turbidity to match the 0.5 McFarland standard.

The suspension was then evenly spread over the surface of a Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) plate supplemented with glucose and methylene blue. Commercial antifungal disks containing specific concentrations of antifungal agents were placed on the inoculated agar surface using sterile forceps, ensuring appropriate spacing between the disks. The plates were incubated at 35°C for 24-48 hours. After incubation, the zones of inhibition around the disks were measured in millimeters using a ruler. The results were interpreted according to the guidelines provided by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) or equivalent standards.

Molecular Identification of biofilm producing candida spp

For 18s rRNA sequencing, a pure fungal culture on chrome agar was sent to MacroGen Korea. Using the most aligned 18s rRNA sequences in the Gene bank of NCBI, a BLAST search was used to identify the unidentified candida species. The findings of the best sequence alignment were noted. To build a phylogenetic tree and analyse evolutionary relationships, MEGA 11 was employed. Using the Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) algorithm, the contig sequences were matched to 18s rRNA sequences in the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) database that were already known. Universal Primers were used for sequencing.

Table 2: Shows the primer sequence for *candida* species.

Species	Primer Name	Sequence (5' → 3')
<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	ITS1	TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG
	ITS4	TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC
<i>Candida krusei</i>	ITS1	TGTTGCTCTAGTTGCTCTT
	ITS4	GCTCTGTTGAGTGTGCTTG
<i>Candida albicans</i>	CA-F1	ATCGATAAGGGTGGCAGGTT
	CA-R1	ATCGATGAAGAACGCAGC
<i>Candida glabrata</i>	ITS1	TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG
	ITS4	TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC

Data Analysis

The data analysis for this research study was performed through Excel 2016.

RESULTS

Samples of Medical Devices

A total of 400 medical devices samples were

collected from different departments of tertiary care hospitals LRH, HMC and KTH. They include urine catheters 19.5%, central venous catheters 8.75%, endotracheal tubes 11.75%, ventilators masks 13.75%, intrauterine devices 18%, dental implants 7%, syringes and IV cannulas 6.50%.

Fig 1: Shows sample percentages of medical devices.

Morphological Characterization

Culture characteristics on the Blood Agar, *Candida spp* shows white colored, smooth, creamy, shiny and yeast-like appearance, on blood agar yellow-white colonies from which "feet" extend out from the margins into the surrounding agar.

appear dark, oval, and polymorphic, cells show single budding.

Microscopic observation

Under the microscope with Gram stain, the cells

Chromogenic assay

All of the yeast isolates tested grew on CHROMagar *Candida*. After 24 h of incubation at 37°C, the majority of yeasts tested had grown well, forming colonies of 1 to 5 mm in diameter. The colony color and characteristics of candida species are given below in the table 3

Table 3: Shows number of isolates and characteristics of *candida* species.

Species	Total number of isolates	Colony characteristics
<i>Candida albicans</i>	53	Apple green colonies
<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	8	Dull blue colonies
<i>Candida krusei</i>	5	Large, flat, spreading, pale pink colonies with matt surfaces
<i>Candida glabrata</i>	21	White large glossy pale pink to violet colonies

Fig 2: Shows *candida* species percentages present in medical devices.

Congo Red Agar

After inoculation and incubation on Congo Red Agar, 16 *Candida* species were identified, of which 7 were *Candida albicans* (43.75%), 4 were *Candida glabra*(25%) , 3 were *Candida tropicalis* (18.75%), and 2 were *Candida krusei*(12.5%) , all of which were biofilm producers. The biofilm-forming colonies appeared dark black, indicating

strong biofilm production. This dark color results from the uptake of Congo red dye by the extracellular biofilm matrix produced by the *Candida* cells. Some of the *Candida* species were weak biofilm producers, displaying colonies with a lighter black color, reflecting a reduced uptake of the dye due to a thinner biofilm matrix.

Fig 3: Shows percentages of biofilm forming *candida* species in medical devices.

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy
 Biofilm extracted from four *Candida* species

(*Candida tropicalis*, *Candida krusei*, *Candida albicans*, and *Candida glabrata*) was used for recording IR spectra in the range of 1000–3200

cm^{-1} . This range was selected to capture the key functional groups present in the biofilm matrix, which includes proteins, polysaccharides, lipids, and other biomolecules essential for biofilm formation and stability. Following below tables and graphs lists shows IR spectroscopy frequency ranges, appearance of the vibration and absorptions for functional groups.

The FTIR spectra of *Candida albicans* contain a variety of bioactive molecules. The 1400 cm^{-1} peak is assigned to the methylene C-H bond, and therefore an alkyl chain is identified. The band at 1230 cm^{-1} associated with phosphorylation of compounds, e.g., phospholipids or nucleic acids, reflects the presence of phosphorylated compounds. The amide II band at 1500 cm^{-1} , NH bending and C-N stretching, characteristic of protein or peptide presence. Alkenes are identified by the 1900 cm^{-1} stretch of C=C while the 2230 cm^{-1} stretch of C \equiv C confirms the presence of alkynes. The CH stretch at 2540 cm^{-1} is indicative of terminal alkynes. The difference of CH₂ at 2750 cm^{-1} and the extension of OH to 3250 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of alcohols and phenols, which are usually found in compounds with hydroxyl. Generally, the sample contains a mixture of alkyl groups, phosphates, proteins, alkynes, and hydroxyl compounds.

The FTIR spectrum of *Candida krusei* reveals the presence of several functional groups. The Amide I band at 1750 cm^{-1} corresponds to C=O stretching of peptide bonds in proteins, indicating the presence of proteins. The peaks at 1065 cm^{-1} and 1035 cm^{-1} are attributed to C-O stretching, which is commonly associated with esters or carbohydrates. The ester carbonyl (C=O) stretching at 1800 cm^{-1} further supports the presence of esters. The C \equiv N stretching at 2150 cm^{-1} suggests the presence of nitriles, while the C \equiv C stretching at 2250 cm^{-1} indicates alkynes. The peak at 2450 cm^{-1} is associated with CO₂ stretching, which could result from carbon

dioxide overtones or a combination band. The peaks at 2850 cm^{-1} and 2950 cm^{-1} correspond to C-H stretching in alkyl groups. Finally, the N-H stretching at 3550 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of amines or amides. Overall, the sample contains a mixture of proteins, esters, nitriles, alkynes, carbon dioxide, alkyl groups, and amines/amides. The FTIR spectrum of the biofilm from *Candida tropicalis* reveals the presence of several key functional groups. The peak at 1150 cm^{-1} indicates C-C stretching from aromatic rings or polymers, suggesting the presence of aromatic compounds or polymeric materials. The Amide II band at 1510 cm^{-1} points to N-H bending, a characteristic of proteins or peptides. The C=O stretching at 2050 cm^{-1} suggests the presence of carboxyl groups (-COOH), which are commonly found in carboxylic acids. The peak at 2300 cm^{-1} corresponds to CO₂ stretching, indicating the presence of carbon dioxide. The O-H stretching at 3100 cm^{-1} is associated with alcohols, while the peak at 2550 cm^{-1} suggests the presence of phenolic compounds. Overall, the biofilm contains a mixture of aromatic compounds, proteins, carboxylic acids, carbon dioxide, alcohols, and phenolic compounds.

The FTIR spectrum of *Candida glabrata* reveals the presence of several key functional groups. The peaks at 1300 cm^{-1} and 1350 cm^{-1} suggest C-H bending from polysaccharides and lipids, indicating the presence of these molecules. The peak at 3220 cm^{-1} corresponds to N-H stretching from amide groups, which is characteristic of proteins or peptides. The C=O stretching at 1800 cm^{-1} points to the presence of carbonyl-containing compounds, such as esters, aldehydes, or fatty acids. The peak at 2400 cm^{-1} suggests the presence of alkynes, while the peak at 2550 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of phenolic compounds. Overall, the sample contains a mixture of lipids, proteins, polysaccharides, and phenolic compounds.

Fig 4: FT-IR analysis of Biofilm produced by *Candida albicans*.

Table 4: Shows the functional groups and corresponding absorption frequencies in FT-IR *Candida albicans*.

Frequency Range	Absorption (cm ⁻¹)	Appearance	Group	Compound Class
C-H Bending	1400	Medium	Methylene	Alkyl Chains
Phosphate Stretching	1230	Strong	P=O Stretching	Phosphates
Amide II Band	1500	Strong	N-H Bending and C-N Stretching	Proteins (Peptides)
C=C Stretching	1900	Weak	Alkenes	Hydrocarbons
C≡C Stretching	2230	Weak	Alkynes	Hydrocarbons
C-H Stretching	2540	Medium	Terminal Alkynes	Hydrocarbons
CH ₂ Deformation	2750	Medium	Methylene	Alkyl Chains
O-H Stretching	3250	Strong	Alcohols and Phenols	Hydroxyl Compounds

Fig 5: FT-IR analysis of Biofilm produced by *Candida krusei*.

Table 5: Shows the functional groups and corresponding absorption frequencies in FT-IR of *Candida krusei*.

Frequency Range	Absorption (cm ⁻¹)	Appearance	Group	Compound Class
Amide I Band	1750	Strong	C=O Stretching (Peptide Bonds)	Proteins
C-O Stretching	1065, 1035	Medium	Ester or Carbohydrates	Esters, Polysaccharides
Ester Carbonyl Stretch	1800	Strong	C=O Stretching	Esters
C≡N Stretching	2150	Medium	Nitriles	Hydrocarbons
C≡C Stretching	2250	Weak	Alkynes	Hydrocarbons
CO ₂ Stretching	2450	Weak	Combination Band/Overtone	Carbon Dioxide
C-H Stretching	2850, 2950	Strong	Alkyl Groups	Hydrocarbons
N-H Stretching	3550	Strong	Amines or Amides	Proteins, Amides

Fig .6: FT-IR analysis of Biofilm produced by *Candida tropicalis*.

Table 6: Shows the functional groups and corresponding absorption frequencies in FT-IR of *Candida tropicalis*.

Frequency Range	Absorption (cm ⁻¹)	Appearance	Group	Compound Class
Mid-Infrared Range	1150	Medium	C-C Stretching	Aromatic Rings, Polymers
Amide II Band	1510	Strong	N-H Bending	Proteins (Peptides)
Carbonyl Stretch	2050	Weak	C=O Stretching	Carboxylic Acids
CO ₂ Stretching	2300	Weak	Stretching	Carbon Dioxide
Hydrogen Bonding Stretch	3100	Strong	O-H Stretching	Alcohols
Phenolic Stretch	2550	Strong	O-H Stretching	Phenolic Compounds

Fig 7: FT-IR analysis of Biofilm produced by *Candida glabrata*.

Table 7: Shows the functional groups and corresponding absorption frequencies in FT-IR of *Candida glabrata*.

Frequency Range	Absorption (cm ⁻¹)	Appearance	Group	Compound Class
C-H Bending	1300	Medium	Polysaccharides and Lipids	Biomolecules
C-H Bending	1350	Medium	Methyl or Methylene Groups	Hydrocarbons
N-H Stretching (Amide A)	3220	Strong	Proteins or Peptides	Amides
C=O Stretching	1800	Strong	Esters, Aldehydes, Ketones, Carboxylic Acids	Carbonyl Compounds
C≡C Stretching	2400	Weak	Alkynes	Hydrocarbons
O-H Stretching	2550	Medium	Phenols	Hydroxyl Compound

Antifungal susceptibility test

The antifungal susceptibility testing of 16 *Candida* isolates showed promising results for some antifungal agents. Fluconazole showed limited effectiveness, with most *Candida* species being resistant. Only 14% of *Candida albicans* samples were susceptible, while *Candida glabrata* and

Candida krusei were completely resistant. Voriconazole performed slightly better, especially against *Candida tropicalis*, where 67% of the samples were susceptible. However, resistance was still significant for *Candida glabrata* (75%) and total for *Candida krusei* (100%). Itraconazole was moderately effective for *Candida albicans* (43%

susceptible) and *Candida tropicalis* (33% susceptible), but the other species, like *Candida glabrata* and *Candida krusei*, were fully resistant.

Amphotericin B emerged as a strong performer, particularly against *Candida tropicalis*, which was 100% susceptible. It also showed good activity against *Candida albicans* (60%) and *Candida glabrata* (75%), but *Candida krusei* was fully resistant. Caspofungin was highly effective for *Candida albicans* (100% susceptible) and showed

good results for *Candida tropicalis* (67%) and *Candida krusei* (50%). However, resistance in half of the *Candida glabrata* and *Candida krusei* samples indicates a need for caution. 5-Flucytosine showed moderate activity, with susceptibility ranging from 33% in *Candida tropicalis* to 50% in *Candida krusei*. Resistance remained relatively high across all species, particularly for *Candida albicans* (65%).

Fig 8: Percentage of Antifungal Susceptibility Profile for *Candida albicans*.

Fig 9: Percentage of Antifungal Susceptibility Profile for *candida glabrata*.

Fig 10: Percentage of Antifungal Susceptibility Profile for *candida tropicalis*.

Fig 11: Percentage of Antifungal Susceptibility Profile for *candida krusei*.

Molecular Identification of biofilm producing *candida* species

The 18s rRNA sequence analysis revealed 99%, 98%, 96% and 97% similarities with *Candida albicans*, *Candida glabrata*, *Candida tropicalis*, and *Candida krusei* as given in figures respectively. The evolutionary history was inferred using the Neighbor-Joining method. The optimal tree is shown. The percentage of replicate trees in which the associated taxa clustered together in the

bootstrap test (1000 replicates) are shown below the branches. The evolutionary distances were computed using the Maximum Composite Likelihood method and are in the units of the number of base substitutions per site. The proportion of sites where at least 1 unambiguous base is present in at least 1 sequence for each descendent clade is shown next to each internal node in the tree. This analysis involved 11 nucleotide sequences. All ambiguous positions

were removed for each sequence pair (pairwise deletion option). There were a total of 40

positions in the final dataset. Evolutionary analyses were conducted in MEGA11.

Fig 12: Showing 99%, similarities with *Candida albicans*,

Fig 13: Showing 98%, similarities with *Candida glabrata*.

Fig 14: Showing 97% similarities with *Candida krusei*.

Fig 15: Showing 96%, similarities with *Candida tropicalis*,

DISCUSSION

Biofilm formation in *Candida* species, particularly *C. albicans*, represents a critical factor contributing to its pathogenicity and resistance to antifungal therapies. Biofilms are structured microbial communities encased in an extracellular matrix that adhere to biotic or abiotic surfaces, such as tissues or medical devices. In clinical settings, biofilm-associated infections are particularly challenging due to their recalcitrance to antifungal treatments and their ability to evade host immune responses.

The present study managed to isolate 87 *Candida* species from different medical devices, with the most seen on urine catheters (19.5%), which was followed by Intrauterine devices (18%), ventilator masks (13.75%) and Endotracheal tubes (11.75%). In the same order, the other devices that have their peculiar attractions to these fungi are central venous catheters (8.75%), dental implants (7%) and syringes/IV cannulas (6.5%). These findings correspond with other studies drawing attention to the interrelationship between medical devices and *Candida* colonization as a result of biofilm formation. For example, Haroon *et al.*, (2024) revealed urinary catheters as the most common source of isolation of *Candida* species (22.3%), Likewise, Moin *et al.*, (2021) recorded that around 10% of central venous catheters in their study had colonization with *Candida* species that corroborated our findings where 8.75% cases had the same. In addition Adnan *et al.*, (2022), where *Candida albicans* was detected in 6.5% of the dental implant-associated biofilms, posited this to the conducive factors that nurtures fungal attachment in the mouth. Colonization rates of syringes and IV cannulas, 6.5% and lower than other devices, are explained by brief exposure period and possibly favorable sterilization measures, as Memon *et al.*, (2021) have observed. Another study by Ali *et al.*, (2020) demonstrated that more often, the use of temporary or permanent biopolymers and medical implements in medicine has escalated the cases of infections associated with the presence of biofilms. One of the clinical specimen positive for HBF *Candida* isolates was catheter. More HBF

Candida was isolated from clinical specimens (vaginal swab, tracheal aspirate, urine) derived from patients' sites that are likely to be indwelled by biomaterials like IUCD, ET tube, and urinary catheter.

The overall results of this study demonstrated that the most frequent species about 13.25% of it was *Candida albicans*, followed by *Candida glabrata* - 5.25%, *Candida tropicalis* - 2.00%, and *Candida krusei* - 1.25%. It was noted that these observations are in line with the global trends as well as *C. albicans* being the predominant species of candidiasis which causes infections related to clinical settings. In contrast to Shoukat *et al.*, (2024), it is known that *C. albicans* is one of the most common species responsible for disseminated candidiasis accounting for 40-60% of the number of isolates due to its ability to produce biofilms and various factors related to virulence. The proportion of *Candida glabrata*, at 5.25%, is consistent with its rising status as a potentially important opportunistic pathogen. This phenomenon has also been noticed by Rattani *et al.*, (2021), who watched increase in the *C. glabrata* infections predominantly in subjects employed in medical fields. Syed *et al.*, (2024) demonstrated a less prevalent role of *C. tropicalis* (2%) and *C. krusei* (1.25%) which were observed in this investigation on the account of high antifungal concentration in the respective regions. *C. tropicalis* has been mostly described with the infections in the tropical climate and also the infections in immunocompromised individuals while as *C. krusei* is characterized by possessing intrinsic resistance against fluconazole, limiting treatment options. A similar finding to the current study was also reported by Fairouz *et al.*, (2020) in which the prevalence of *C. krusei* and *C. glabrata*, they were 9.4% and 6.3% from aprons/scrubs.

The fact that this study identified 16 species of *Candida* including, *C. albicans* 43.75%, *C. glabrata* 25%, *C. tropicalis* 18.75% and *C. krusei* 12.5%, all as biofilm producers, shows the polymorphism of these pathogens and their clinical importance. In contrast to Alikhani *et al.*, (2022) *C. albicans* was shown by as the dominant *Candida* species in

West Ahvaz medical centers. About 78 % of the isolates obtained were identified as *C. albicans*, while *C. glabrata* was isolated at a rate of 22%. It is important to note that 48.7% of the isolates *C. albicans* biofilm forming isolates and 54.5% of the *C. glabrata* isolates are biofilm producers. The results indicated that the Non albicans Candidiasis held higher adhesion ability than *C. albicans*. The biofilm forming ability of various *Candida* species varied significantly and variations in biofilm formation might be due to different experimental techniques employed. It is of interest to note that *C. parapsilosis* had the most robust biofilm-forming ability while *C. glabrata* showed limited total biomass and metabolic activity. A similar study by Zuo *et al.*, (2021), who noted notable variation in biofilm production among various *Candida* species, are corroborated by this. While *Candida glabrata* showed the lowest biofilm biomass and metabolic activity, non-albicans *Candida* species, especially *C. parapsilosis*, showed greater adhesion ability than *C. albicans*, indicating a varied biofilm-forming potential among species. Heaney *et al.*, (2020) illustrated quite a contrast to what the present study has sought to establish. Some former studies showed that *C. parapsilosis*, *C. glabrata*, & *C. tropicalis* possess stronger ability to form biofilms which could sustain higher mortality rates in both in vivo and in vitro analysis. Of particular concern is the strong *C. parapsilosis* that forms biofilms in medical implants which may also increase the overall virulence. Furthermore, *C. tropicalis* clinical isolates feature a biofilm formation rate of 71.4%, which is far higher than the 22.6% performance of *C. albicans*, and accents the fact that certain non-albicans species of NCAC are more voracious in forming biofilms on artificial surfaces that increase virulence and consequently mortality rates. On the other hand, reduced rate of biofilm formation was seen in *C. albicans* isolates suggesting that chronic and difficult to treat infections could be more pronounced in non-albicans *Candida* species making such clinical settings highly dangerous.

The FTIR spectral characteristics of biofilms from the clinical strains: *Candida albicans*, *Candida*

krusei, *Candida tropicalis* and *Candida glabrata* can therefore help in exposing the functional groups within the biofilm matrix which aids in the pathogenicity and the biofilm structural stability. Peaks from the FTIR spectra are due to the presence of proteins, polysaccharides, lipids and phenolic compounds as established in the literature earlier. For example, *C. albicans* biofilm matrix containing alkyl group, phosphates and proteins is consistent with the conclusion of studies by Chirman *et al.*, (2021) and Pebotuwa *et al.*, (2020) which showed that *C. albicans* biofilm forming strain is highly resistant to antifungal agents. Biofilm production in *C. glabrata* isolates was also recorded to be high and these biofilms are reported to contain lipids and proteins as also reported by Palencia *et al.*, (2022) regarding the pathogenicity of biofilm forming *C. glabrata*. Biofilms of *C. tropicalis* bearing aromatic gr and carboxylic acid retain strong biofilm forming capacities that are in agreement with Dheeb *et al.*, (2023) findings that *C. tropicalis* biofilm formation increases resistance to antifungals. These results indicate that the capacity to produce competent biofilms as well as the composition of the biofilm matrix is important for Candidiasis dispersion and survival in the clinical amphiarthrosis. For *C. albicans*, the presence of alkyl chains, phosphates, and proteins correlates with Esfahani *et al.*, (2024) who found similar bio molecules augmenting bio film. According to Yadav *et al.*, (2022), *C. glabrata* has a high lipid and protein content that supports their antifungal resistance. In a similar study, *C. tropicalis* was also reported to be a strong biofilm producer according to Senthilganesh *et al.*, (2022). For *C. krusei*, nitriles and esters were noted emphasizing their importance to adherence and virulence. Such observations suggest that, matrix composition is an important focus in the development of antifungal therapies.

The antifungal susceptibility testing of 16 *Candida* isolates produced biofilms which are in consistent with those of several other studies. *C. albicans*' susceptibility rates were only 14%, reflecting the 20-30% resistance rate against biofilm forming strains reported by Lamsal *et al.*,

(2021). Likewise, complete resistance was observed in *C. glabrata* and *C. krusei* has emphasized in an international literature review by Lee *et al.*, (2021). Moderate efficacy of voriconazole was noted mostly on *C. tropicalis* 67%, consistent with Jafri *et al.*, (2020) who found its efficacy on possible azole sensitive infections despite resistance associated to biofilms. Amphotericin B was highly effective especially to *C. tropicalis* at 100% level. Nonetheless, *C. krusei* remained resistant in concord to observations made by Al-Shamahy *et al.*, (2020). Caspofungin was effective on *C. albicans* at 100% and moderately effective on *C. tropicalis* at 67%, with partial resistance incidences on *C. glabrata* and *C. krusei* consistent with findings by Radunovic *et al.*, (2022). *C. tropicalis* was susceptible at 33% while *C. krusei* was at 50% with flucytosine revealing moderate activity that is consistent with that from Ahmad *et al.*, (2020). Jointly, these findings highlight the problem of antifungal resistance in *Candida* species able to produce biofilm, and stress the importance of applying some combination therapy, as well as focusing on the antifungal drugs. According to another study in Greece as described by the authors Chatzimoschou *et al.*, (2021), specifically the fluconazole resistance emerges mostly in *Candida auris* isolates, as one of the Iranian isolates resisted fluconazole out of the many. Fluconazole resistant biofilm forming isolates had on average between 1000-2000 times higher MIC values for triazoles, echinocandins and amphotericin B than free floating cells. For amphotericin B, liposomal formulation showed less efficacy against biofilms in comparison to deoxycholate formulation, which had almost the same efficacy for both biofilm and free floating cells these results pointed *C. auris* biofilm resistance as a therapeutic problem. *C. albicans* is the most frequent species capable of biofilm production among *Candida* species owing to its distinct pathogenic characteristics. Through an arsenal of adhesions, it however sticks efficiently to range of surfaces like host tissues and medical implants. Biofilms of *C. albicans* are quite complex in terms of their architecture and basic

composition as they contain large amounts of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) providing structural stability and antifungal drug resistance. Its phenotypic switching, the switching between yeast and filamentous forms is also believed to facilitate transition from biofilm formation process to immune evasion. Hydrolytic enzymes, for example, are virulence factors which are known to enhance biofilm production and pathogenicity. In a different study in Nepal conducted by Lamsal *et al.*, (2021), the antifungal susceptibility patterns displayed by the *Candida albicans* isolated strains were high susceptibility to fluconazole (80.9%), amphotericin B (76.19%), and clotrimazole (80.9%). But biofilm associated forms of *C. albicans* had higher MIC by a factor of two and eight when compared with planktonic cells suggesting large antifungal resistance. This also reinforces the concern loomed by biofilm forming *C. albicans* in providing correct medical treatment, which is in this case, a well targeted solution towards the antifungal resistance posed by the biofilms.

CONCLUSION

The research study highlights the alarming prevalence of biofilm-forming *Candida* species on medical devices in tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar, posing a significant threat to patient safety. With prevalence of 16 *Candida* isolates revealed high resistance to fluconazole, voriconazole, and itraconazole, especially in *Candida glabrata* and *Candida krusei*. Amphotericin B and caspofungin showed the most promise, with high susceptibility in *Candida albicans* and *Candida tropicalis*, though partial resistance was observed in some species. These findings highlight the importance of species-specific testing to guide effective antifungal therapy and address rising resistance. The findings revealed that a significant proportion of *Candida* isolates were capable of forming biofilms, a key virulence factor contributing to persistent infections and resistance to antifungal agents. Amphotericin B and caspofungin demonstrated higher efficacy against most *Candida* species, while azoles, such as fluconazole, exhibited limited effectiveness.

These results underscore the need for targeted antifungal therapy and improved infection control measures to manage Candida-related infections effectively.

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